

HARMONISED PRACTICES, REGULATIONS AND STANDARDS
IN WASTE MANAGEMENT AND DECOMMISSIONING

Deliverable D2.3

Updated Description of Action

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ABSTRACT

This document details the initial Description of Action, after the selection of the 9 priority topics and the addition of 4 new beneficiaries. The update considers both a technical update of the planned work in WP's 3, 4 and 5, where more details are added and an update on the staff effort (manpower) per WP.

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Version history

Version	Date	Author	Comments
V0.1	22-04-2024	Elke Jacops	Version for review by the management team
V0.2	30-04-2024	Réka Szőke	Reviewed version
V1.0	30-04-2024	Elke Jacops	Final version

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Updated DoA for WP3

Objectives

This work package aims to identify the most important needs and opportunities for current and future cross border radioactive waste management activities (i.e., characterisation, treatment, conditioning, and storage) and assess regulatory obstacles to providing such services (with WP6). The outcomes will provide MS, the EC and other interested stakeholders with guidance on advancing safe and efficient cross border service/facility possibilities in radioactive waste management.

Description

Task 3.2 - Refinement (Phases 1b and 2), M12-30. Lead = Studsvik, Partners = SOGIN, UJV, IRSN, NUCLECO, RATEN, JAVYS, GSL, CYCLIFE, MERIENCE

This task starts with Open Call linkage (Task 2.3, M12-18) and then engages deeper with stakeholders identified in WP2, to further evaluate issues associated with the top three prioritised subthemes (from Task 3.1). Key partners have been selected to contribute to the subtheme work, then progressing with stakeholder engagement actions linked with WP7.

Task 3.2a: To align wastes with treatment technologies in a manner acceptable to all stakeholders (Lead = STUDSVIK, Partners = MERIENCE, JAVYS, NUCLECO, CYCLIFE)

A common understanding of the suitability of treatment options for different waste types is required to establish new shared waste processing opportunities but also a way to make decision makers aware of possible options so conscious decisions can be made. The Task recognizes that stakeholders may have differing views on the suitability of treatment options for certain wastes.

Task 3.2b: Harmonisation of Individual EU and international countries problematic waste inventory (Lead = JAVYS (lead), Partners = STUDSVIK, IRSN, RATEN, ENEA)

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A common understanding of the suitability of treatment options for different waste types is required to establish new shared waste processing opportunities. The Task recognizes that stakeholders may have differing views on the suitability of treatment options for certain wastes.

Task 3.2c: Member States approach to dealing with radioactive contaminated hazardous waste differs (Lead = GSL, Partners = LEI, RATEN, SOGIN)

Identification of barriers to the treatment of radioactively contaminated hazardous waste within and between MS and to also identify any learning from the development of hazardous waste treatment from outside the nuclear industry (i.e. not radioactively contaminated waste).

Task 3.3 – Regulatory Impact, M24-M32 (Lead = JAVYS, Studsvik, SOGIN, IRSN, RATEN)

This task will provide a summary of the regulatory impacts associated with the topics under WP3, which will be shared with WP6 to collate.

Task 3.4 - Business Case, M24-M32, works with WP2 to set their outcome (Lead = Cyclife, partners = Studsvik, SOGIN, UJV, Nucleco, RATEN, JAVYS, GSL)

The TECOP (Technical, Environmental, Commercial, Operational, Political/Social) process (a risk analysis framework used to assess and manage risks) will identify a multitude of potential changes, which will require further review in conjunction with WP2 on business impacts for stakeholders across all MS, focused on strategic impacts across EU.

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Updated DoA for WP4

Objectives

Work package 4 aims to identify the most important conditions and opportunities for promoting circular economy when managing materials and waste coming from nuclear decommissioning across Europe.

Based on the outcomes of Task 4.1 (Deliverable D4.1 – “Prioritisation of identified topics (WP4)” - 30.06.2023), three themes have been identified for deeper analysis in Phase 2. Key partners have been selected to contribute to the subtheme work based on the outcome of WP2 open call (Task 2.3).

In the following sections the description objective and methodology to deliver the objective, for the three sub-tasks, are reported together with the list of Partners involved in the action.

Description

Task 4.2 - Refinement (Phases1b and 2), M12-30. (Lead = SOGIN. Partners: Amphos21, Andra, BelV, Center for Energy Research, CEPN, Cyclife, ENEA, GSL, IFE, JRC, Laborelec/Tractabel, LEI, NNL, ORANO, SCK-CEN, Studsvik, SURO, UJV Rez).

This task will start with Open Call linkage (Task 2.3, M12-18) and then engage deeper with stakeholders identified from WP2, to further evaluate issues associated with the top three prioritised subthemes (from Task 4.1). Key partners have been selected to contribute to the subtheme work, then progressing with stakeholder engagement actions linked with WP7, using the TECOP approach.

- **Task 4.2a - National regulations and criteria for Clearance, M18-M30 (Lead= UJV Rez. Partners: BelV, ENEA, JRC, LEI, ORANO, SCK-CEN, SOGIN, SURO)**

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This sub-task will analyse the differences between national regulations, release criteria and methodological approaches, and their impact on the reuse and recycling of waste. The expected outcome of the sub-task is to identify the advantages and weaknesses of the different national approaches, as well as the points that could be balanced through greater cooperation and/or recommending good practice for wider use.

- Task 4.2b - Benchmarking of Circular Economy Approaches and Technologies, M18-M30 (Lead= **CEPN**. Partners: Andra, IFE, NNL, GSL, SOGIN, Laborelec/Tractabel)

This sub-task will collect and analyse actual examples and case studies (in and outside the nuclear field) outlining implementation of Circular Economy approaches and technologies to the decommissioning of nuclear facilities and related radioactive waste and materials management. The expected outcome of the sub-task is to support decision makers ability to make strategies and decisions for more sustainable decommissioning and for minimising waste and recovering and reusing valuable materials.

- Task 4.2c - Sustainability Assessment, M18-M30 (Lead= **Amphos21**. Partners: Andra, Center for Energy Research, CEPN, SCK-CEN)

This sub-task will identify the differences between the sustainability assessment methodologies, their main drivers and barriers, and its potential for harmonization. The expected outcome is to set up a robust decision support framework that enables the comparison between linear and circular economy approaches in radioactive waste management and decommissioning.

Outcome = The provision of position papers (deliverables) based on the task data and the detailed feedback from the stakeholders engaged with a series of recommendations using the TECOP approach.

Task 4.3 – Regulatory Impact, M24-M32 (Lead = CEPN, partners = Studsvik, SOGIN, NNL, BeIV, SURO, LEI)

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This task will provide summary of the regulatory impacts associated with the topics and will provide Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats for the WP4 topics.

WP6 will then collate the impacts and prepare a summary memo identifying relevant regulatory differences.

Task 4.4 - Business Case, M24-M32, works with WP2 to set their outcome (Lead = GSL, partners = SOGIN, NNL, Amphos21, Andra, CEPN, LEI, GSL, ORANO, Cyclife)

The TECOP process will identify a multitude of potential changes, which will require further review in conjunction with WP2 on business impacts for stakeholders across all MS, focused on strategic impacts across EU.

Updated DoA for WP5

Objectives

This work package aims to (a) identify the obstacles and issues that could hamper the implementation of advanced technologies in waste management and decommissioning, (b) identify opportunities for more aligned practices, methodologies and approaches across MS, and (c) investigate and conclude on the need and benefits of the adoption of and more aligned approach to advanced technologies to enhance waste management and decommissioning operations in Europe.

Description

Task 5.2 - Refinement (Phases 1b and 2), M12-30. Lead = NNL, partners = Studsvik, GRS, IRSN, VTT, ORANO, IFE, CYCLIFE, CAEN, JRC, CEA, ENEA, NUCLECO

This task starts with Open Call linkage (Task 2.3, M12-18) and then engages deeper with stakeholders identified from WP2, to further evaluate issues associated with the

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top three prioritised subthemes (from Task 5.1). Key partners have been selected to contribute to the subtheme work, then progressing with stakeholder engagement actions linked with WP7.

Task 5.2a Standardising approaches to technology assessment and qualification for decontamination, environmental restoration, waste treatment and immobilisation (Lead = NNL, partners = Studsvik, GRS, VTT, ORANO, CYCLIFE, CAEN)

This task will investigate the challenges around technology assessment and qualification of new innovative technologies in waste management and decommissioning and identify where standardised approaches could facilitate adoption of these technologies.

Task 5.2b Standardising protocols and systems to support adoption of robotics and automation in decommissioning, dismantling and waste management (Lead = GRS, partners = VTT, NNL, IFE, CAEN, ENEA)

This task will identify enablers and blockers to the adoption of robotics and automation and their cost benefits, consider a standardised taxonomy/categorisation principle to facilitate a graded approach and identify where standardisation could facilitate adoption of robotics and automation.

Task 5.2c Standardising digital twin and advanced Building Information Management (BIM) technology and their application (Lead = IFE, partners = IRSN, JRC, NUCLECO, CEA)

The standardization of DT and advanced BIM presents several, and sometimes unique challenges in the nuclear industry that need to be analysed, along with the expected impact and scope. This task will identify the enablers and blockers for standardising DT and advanced BIM, benefits and challenges for common approaches, and their application, including their impact. The task will also identify to what extent, how and where standardisation could facilitate large scale adoption of DT and BIM in the nuclear sector.

Outcome = The provision of a position paper on adoption of advanced technologies (deliverable) based on the task data from Tasks 5.2a, b and c and the detailed

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feedback from the stakeholders engaged, with a series of recommendations taking account of the TECOP (Technical, Environmental, Commercial, Operational, Political/Social) or a similar approach.

Task 5.3 – Regulatory Impact, M24-M32 (Lead = ENEA, partners = Studsvik, IFE, NNL, VTT, GRS, IRSN, NUCLECO, ORANO, CYCLIFE, JRC, CEA)

This task will provide a summary of the regulatory impacts associated with the topics under WP5, which will be shared with WP6 to collate.

Task 5.4 - Business Case, M24-M32, works with WP2 to set their outcome (Lead = IFE, partners = Studsvik, NNL, VTT, GRS, CAEN, ORANO, NUCLECO, CYCLIFE, JRC, CEA)

The TECOP process will identify a multitude of potential changes, which will require further review in conjunction with WP2 on business impacts for stakeholders across all MS, focused on strategic impacts across EU.

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Update of manpower

After setting the 9 priority topics, an Open Call was launched with a two-fold objective. First, to attract new beneficiaries to strengthen the consortium in Phase 2 when working on the priority topics. Second, to allow all partners to refine their choice of topics to work on in Phase 2. When the project was initiated, partners made an initial selection of the WP where they were interested in. After setting the priority topics, some partners preferred to work on topics of work packages, other than the one for which they initially signed up. This change was often related to changes in interest of the organisation, changes of priorities or staff.

This refinement lead do a redistribution of the work of the project partners in Phase 2. For each partner, the total amount of man months remained the same, only the distribution over the WP's has changed. The overview of manpower per WP and per partner is shown in Table 1.

The changes listed in this document will be approved by the project's General Assembly and will lead to a new amendment of the project.

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Table 1: Update of manpower for Phase 2

	Organisation	Country	WP distribution in PM (person month)							PM total per organisation
			WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	WP7	
1	SCK CEN	BE	10	5.5		4		2	2	23.50
2	Studsvik	SE			5.5	0.5	1	0.5		7.5
3	SOGIN	IT	2	2	2	5.5		2	1	14.5
4	VTT	FI	2	3			2	7.5	2	16.5
5	ENEA	IT	2	2	1	2	1.5	2	4	14.5
6	Bel V	BE		1.5		2		4	0.5	8
7	SURO	CZ		1.5		2		4.5	0.5	8.5
8	ÚJV	CZ		2.5		4			0.5	7
9	GRS	DE		1.5			4	2	0.5	8
10	Amphos 21	ES		1.5		4			2	7.5
11	MERIENCE	ES		1.5	2			2	0.5	6
12	ANDRA	FR		1.5		4			0.5	6
13	CEPN	FR		1.5		4.5			0.5	6.5
14	IRSN	FR		1.5	2		2	4.5	0.5	10.5
15	CAEN	IT		1.5			4		0.5	6
16	NUCLECO	IT		1.5	3		1		0.5	6
17	LEI	LT		1.5	2	2			0.5	6
18	RATEN	RO		1.5	4				1.5	7
19	JAVYS	SK		1	5				0.5	6.5
20	ORANO	FR		1.5		2	2		0.5	6

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21	Cyclife-EDF	FR		1.5	2	0.5	2		0.5	6.5
22	IFE	NO	5	2		1	4	2	4	18
23	NNL	UK	2	2		2	5.5	2	1	14.5
24	GSL	UK		2.5	2	2.5			0.5	7.5
25	Studsvik ltd	UK	2	2	2				1	7
26	JRC	EUR				2	1	1	1	5
27	EK	HU				1.75				1.75
28	Laborelec	BE				0.875				0.875
29	Tractebel	BE				0.875				0.875
30	CEA	FR					1.75			1.75
TOTAL			25	45.5	32.5	48	31.75	36	27	245.75